

OUR CITIZENSHIP IS IN HEAVEN

AN EXEGETICAL ESSAY AND ANALYSIS OF PHILIPPIANS 3:20-21

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I. Thesis:

The *thesis* of this exegetical essay is that in Philippians 3:20-21, Paul contrasts earthly and heavenly citizenship to define believers' true allegiance ("worthy of the gospel") and he points to ("heavenly citizenry") in Christ.¹ Paul motivates and encourages believers "to eagerly wait" and reminds them of the anticipated promise of the "glorious body in Christ."² Paul offers the Philippians both a hope and joy that sustains them in adversity and a motivation and encouragement to live with an eternal mindset (eschatological focus).

II. Introduction:

A. (Philippians 3:20-21) - The New English Translation (NET) Bible:

Philippians 3:20-21: "(20) But our citizenship is in heaven—and we also eagerly await a savior from there, the Lord Jesus Christ, (21) who will transform these humble bodies of ours (6) into the likeness of his glorious body by means of that power by which he is able to subject all things to himself."³

¹ Michael Gorman writes on page (pg) 500: "Paul begins and ends this major section of the letter (Phil 1:27-2:18) on the theme of unity for the sake of witness in *suffering* (Phil. 1:27-30 and Phil. 2:14-18). That is, the 'Christ-poem' is set between missional bookends. The Philippians have opponents (1:28) and are *suffering* for Christ (1:29). This occasion provides Paul with the opportunity to issue a fundamental exhortation and one of the governing metaphors of the letter: in 1:27 he calls the Philippians to live out their lives as citizens (*politeuesthe*, related to *polis*, 'city,' as noted above) (12) in a manner 'worthy of the gospel' of Christ, the gospel that will be rehearsed in Phil. 2:6-11. To be worthy of citizenship is to bring *honor* rather than shame to the city, its rulers, and its traditions. Gorman footnotes on (pg) 500 (12): "NRSV (like most translations) has the bland 'live your life.'" N.T. Wright's *Kingdom New Testament* has "your public behavior must match up to the gospel of the king." Ibid., 500; N.T. Wright, *The Kingdom New Testament: A Contemporary Translation* (New York: HarperOne, 2011), Phil. 1:27, 217-220.

² Justo González (Cuban-American theologian) writes on (pg) 49 about the "glorious body": "The Savior will transform believers radically, so that "the body of our *humiliation*" will be "conformed to the *body* of his *glory*." And if anyone wonders how this Savior will do such a thing, Paul responds that he will do it with his own sustaining and creating power, "the power that also enables him to make all things subject to himself." Justo L. González, *Three Months with Paul* (Nashville, TN: Abingdon Press, 2006), 49.

³ Michael Gorman cautions ministers and students in his book *Elements of Biblical Exegesis* on Page (52) that the following translations (tns) are preferred for exegesis: (NRSV, NAB, TNIV, and NET). He contends that NRSV out of the four (tns) is the

B. (Philippians 3:20-21) - The New Revised Standard Version (NRSV) Bible:

Philippians 3:20-21: “(20) But our citizenship (d) is in heaven, and it is from there that we are expecting a Savior, the Lord Jesus Christ. (21) He will transform the body of our humiliation (e) that it may be conformed to the body of his glory, (f) by the power that also enables him to make all things subject to himself.”⁴

Philippians is attributed by most scholars, professors, and theologians to the Apostle Paul (c. 5 – 68 AD) and is generally dated for historical clarity and context to the period of his imprisonment in Rome (60 – 62 AD).⁵ This historical context helps to stress the themes of hope and endurance during challenging circumstances. Paul’s letter surpasses the sum of its parts (meaning that the letter he is writing transcends outside of the papyri). The Philippian letter in particular was written during Paul’s *imprisonment* and is in a lot of ways one of his better works

best to use for exegesis. He relays that (ESV, NIV, and NASB) are useful for exegesis but with *caution*. Moreover, he argues that (KJV, NKJV, and LB) are unacceptable for exegesis. Abbreviations: chapter (ch), Page (pg), translation(s) (tn/tns), verse (v), verses (vv), Old Testament (OT), Hebrew (Heb.), the New Testament (NT), and Greek (Grk). Michael J. Gorman, *Elements of Biblical Exegesis: A Basic Guide for Students and Ministers*, Rev. and Exp. ed. (Grand Rapids, MI: Baker Academic, 2009), 52; Footnote of (v) Phil. 3:21 (6) (tn) (Grk): “Transform the body of our humility.” *The NET Bible: New English Translation*, 2nd ed. (Richardson, TX: Biblical Studies Press, 1997), 2157, Phil. 3:20-21.

⁴ Footnote and other (Grk) meanings: d (Or commonwealth), e (Or our humble bodies), f (Or his glorious body). (vv) 3:18–19: Many live as enemies of the cross of Christ, presumably professing Christians who cannot accept Paul’s theology of the cross. (v) 20: Our citizenship, our ultimate political loyalty and real homeland, contrasting with the status of most of the Philippians as Roman citizens. (v) 21: (Rom. 8:23; 1 Cor. 15:47-57; 2 Cor. 5:1-15; Col. 3:1-4; Col. 4:1; 1 Thess. 2:19-20). A crown was often awarded to the winner of a race. Michael D. Coogan, Marc Z. Brettler, and Carol Newsom, eds., *The New Oxford Annotated Bible with Apocrypha: New Revised Standard Version* (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2010), 2065, Phil. 3:20-21.

⁵ The authorship of *Philippians* by the Apostle Paul is generally accepted by scholars. However, to uphold this belief Michael Gorman writes on (pg) 496: “Having completed his prayer for the Philippians and affirmed both their participation in his ‘*prison ministry*’ and his confidence in their faithfulness to the end, Paul proceeds to describe the impact of his current *imprisonment* on both the gospel and himself. . . . As he begins the body of his letter, Paul wants to assure the Philippians that, unexpectedly and contrary to their concerns, his imprisonment has advanced rather than hindered the gospel (Phil. 1:12), and this is in two main ways. First Paul’s captors (or those in control of his place of imprisonment), (9) as well as everyone else aware of his situation, know that he is imprisoned for Christ (Phil. 1:13).” Gorman footnotes on (pg) 496 (9): “That is, the “*imperial guard*” (NRSV; NIV, “*palace guard*”) or “*praetorium*” (NAB; NIV mg., “*whole palace*”). There is disagreement over the meaning of the (Grk) word *praitōrion*, translating the Latin (Ltn) word *praetorium*, in Phil. 1:13. Does it refer to a body of people or to a residence, and was it located only in Rome or also in the provincial capitals?” Michael J. Gorman, *Apostle of the Crucified Lord: A Theological Introduction to the Pauline Epistles*, 2nd ed. (Grand Rapids: Eerdmans, 2017), 496; Paul likely wrote *Philippians* in 61-62 AD. Stanley E. Porter, *The Apostle Paul: His Life, Thought, and Letters* (Grand Rapids, MI: William B. Eerdmans Publishing Company, 2016), 398.

due to it being written with a sense of urgency and shaped by his experience in *prison*.⁶

The *hymn-like* tone of his writing in Philippians can be likened to the formation of a diamond under great pressure.⁷ Due to this pressure it results in a profound and robust resonant melody of faith and *persuasion*.⁸ Each chapter of *Philippians* is building, and building, and building up on itself like a cresting wave that ultimately crashes onto the seashore. Paul is acting like God's little conductor who masterfully puts together (weaves back and forth) and orchestrates God's symphony. This progression seen in *Philippians* not only deepens Paul's theological insights but also serves to encourage the Philippians in their faith journey, reinforcing themes of joy, unity, and perseverance in the face of adversity. Paul emphasizes the importance of unity and mutual support among believers urging them to "stand firm in one spirit" and "striving side by side".⁹ To draw from the analogy of "trench warfare" from World War I, Paul is asking us believers to stand alongside one another "in the trenches" and helping each other out as we face all kinds of

⁶ Michael Gorman writes on (pg) 497: "Paul's words about his indifference to impure motives, and about the present impact of his *imprisonment* on the gospel and on others, turn now into a moving meditation on his own future. It is linked to what immediately precedes it by the mention of *rejoicing* (Phil 1:18), but its actual subject matter is first announced in (Phil. 1:19) and then, forming *inclusio*, repeated in (Phil. 1:25-26)." Michael J. Gorman, *Apostle of the Crucified Lord: A Theological Introduction to the Pauline Epistles*, 2nd ed. (Grand Rapids: Eerdmans, 2017), 497.

⁷ Michael Gorman footnotes on (pg.) (492) (5): "The claim that Phil. 2:6-11 is an early *Christian hymn* is now questioned by many, though the scholarly jury is still out. The first edition of this book called it a *hymn*; some refer to it as a 'prose hymn.' It is sometimes considered an encomium, or tribute (e.g., Gordon Zerbe). I will use terms such as 'story,' 'drama,' 'poem,' 'poetic story,' 'Christ-poem,' and even 'gospel' interchangeably. If it also a *hymn*, none of these other designations is invalidated." Michael J. Gorman, *Apostle of the Crucified Lord: A Theological Introduction to the Pauline Epistles*, 2nd ed. (Grand Rapids: Eerdmans, 2017), 492.

⁸ James Thompson notes on Page 130 about the Apostle Paul and his persuasion: "In the opening thanksgiving, Paul reassures the community that, despite its precarious situation, "the one who began a good work among [them] will bring it to completion at the day of Christ" (Phil 1:6), and he prays that the community will be "pure and blameless" at the day of Christ (Phil. 1:10)... The primary exemplum is the poetic narrative in (Phil. 2:6-11), Paul's most extended Christological statement. This exemplum may already be known to the community; thus it probably has special *persuasive force*." James W. Thompson, *Apostle of Persuasion: Theology and Rhetoric in the Pauline Letters* (Grand Rapids, MI: Baker Academic, 2020), 130.

⁹ The concept of unity and mutual support is tied to Phil. 3:20-21 and is best expressed in the Phil. 1:27 NRSV: "Only, live for your life in a manner worthy of the gospel of Christ, so that, whether I come and see you or am absent and hear about you, I will know that you are *standing firm in one spirit, striving side by side* with one mind for the faith of the gospel." *The New Oxford Annotated Bible with Apocrypha: New Revised Standard Version* (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2010), 2063, Phil. 1:27.

adversity at every turn.¹⁰ As Paul weaves together personal reflection and communal exhortation, he invites the readers of the letter (also his intended audience) to embody the *mind of Christ*.¹¹

III. Historical and Literary Context:

Paul directs this letter to the Philippian believers, emphasizing themes of identity in Christ and transformation. *Philippi* (ancient city in Macedonia, Greece) was a renowned Roman colony where citizenship held substantial social and political value, shaping the identity and loyalties of its residents. As a major trade route, *Philippi* was strategically located along what was called “The Egnatian Way (Latin: Via Egnatia),” linking the city to other prominent regions of the Roman Empire and enhancing its economic importance. Its status as a Roman colony also meant that many of its inhabitants were veterans and Roman citizens, instilling a unique blend of Roman culture and loyalty within the local population.¹² The literary context of Philippians is

¹⁰ John Keegan provides an in-depth analysis and narrates the nuances of “trench warfare”, including its strategies, impacts, and experiences of soldiers on the Western Front. Keegan’s work is highly praised by scholars making it a commonly cited source for discussing “trench warfare”. John Keegan, *The First World War* (New York: Alfred A. Knopf, 1999), 176-179. 2 Corinthians 4:8-9 reads: “We are *afflicted in every way*, but not crushed; perplexed, but not driven to despair; persecuted, but not forsaken; struck down, but not destroyed.” This passage emphasizes the resilience of believers amidst trials and tribulations, reassuring them that while they may face numerous hardships, they are never abandoned or defeated. Footnote on page 2030 vv 8-9: Catalogue of hardships formulated as antithetical pairs to show the incomparable power of God’s glory. *The New Oxford Annotated Bible with Apocrypha: New Revised Standard Version* (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2010), 2030, 2 Corinthians 4:8-9.

¹¹ The concept of having the “mind of Christ” is central to Paul’s message in Philippians, encouraging followers to reflect Christ’s attitude in their own lives. Philippians 2:5 NRSV states: “Let the same mind be in you that was (a) in Christ Jesus.” (Grk) meaning (a): “Or that you have”. Footnote on page 2063: Phil. 1:27-4:4: Appeal to unity, to be followed by examples. *The New Oxford Annotated Bible with Apocrypha: New Revised Standard Version* (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2010), 2063, Phil. 2:5.

¹² The photograph at the top of (pg) 833 was taken by Howard Vos. The photograph’s caption reads: “Ruins of the agora, or marketplace, of *Philippi*, with a pagan temple in the foreground.” Lockyer states on (pg) 833: “Philippi [FIL uh pie] (*city of Philip*) – a city in eastern Macedonia (modern Greece) visited by the Apostle Paul. Situated on a plain surrounded by mountains, *Philippi* lay about 16 kilometers (10 miles) inland from the Aegean Sea. The Egnatian Way (Latin: Via Egnatia), the main overland route between Asia and the West, ran through the city. *Philippi* was named for Philip II of Macedonia (c. 382 BC – 336 BC), the father of Alexander the Great (c. 356 BC – 323 BC).” Herbert Lockyer, Sr., ed., *Nelson’s Illustrated Bible Dictionary* (Nashville, TN: Thomas Nelson Publishers, 1986), 833; Paul Stanley writes about the Greco-Roman analogy of the body (residents) and references Galatians 3:28: Stanley E. Porter, *The Apostle Paul: His Life, Thought, and Letters* (Grand Rapids, MI:

essential for interpreting its themes and message. The Philippians had sent him financial support and were concerned about his well-being, prompting Paul to express gratitude and encouragement in his response.¹³ Within the letter of *Philippians* there are four (4) key themes and structures: joy and encouragement, unity and community, Christ-centered living, and its eschatological focus.

IV. Exegesis of Philippians 3:20-21:

A. Commentary Insights:

I will draw from two commentaries (one from Holloway and one from Hawthorne) below that both deduce Paul's view of believers' primary identity as being in Christ ("heavenly citizenship") rather than rooted in earthly nationality, citizenry, or status ("of [on] the earth"). This perspective challenges understandings of identity, urging believers to recognize their ultimate belonging in the spiritual realm of heaven. By prioritizing this "heavenly citizenship," Paul calls for unity among believers that transcends cultural and social divisions.¹⁴ This emphasis on "heavenly citizenship" is crucial for understanding Paul's theological framework, which positions believers as part of a new community that is defined not by things of this world but by their identity in Jesus Christ. Such a *paradigm shift* encourages a sense of belonging that fosters

William B. Eerdmans Publishing Company, 2016), 412.

¹³ Paul thanks the Philippians for their financial support in his letter (ch) 4 (vv) 15-16 NRSV: "(15) You Philippians indeed know that in the early days of the gospel, when I left Macedonia, no church shared with me in the matter of giving and receiving, except you alone. (16) For even when I was in Thessalonica, you sent me help for my needs more than once." *The New Oxford Annotated Bible with Apocrypha: New Revised Standard Version* (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2010), 2065, Phil. 4:15-16.

¹⁴ Justo González writes on (pg) 49: "In contrast to such people, true believers know that "our citizenship is in heaven." True believers hope in the Lord, who comes from heaven—and not in something that is *earthly* or serves their own belly, as do the enemies of the cross." Justo L. González, *Three Months with Paul* (Nashville, TN: Abingdon Press, 2006), 49.

mutual support and accountability among believers.¹⁵ I contend that *Philippians* is the Apostle Paul's Opus and he is building a crescendo of great magnitude to contrast earth versus heaven.

B. Hermeneia Commentary:

Paul Holloway writes on page 179 at footnote (18): “For “citizenship,” see my comment above on Philippians 1:27 (Referring to Page 105).”¹⁶ Holloway footnotes (6 and 7) on page 105: “Here in 1:27 he urges the Philippians to act in a manner worthy of the gospel (1:27a) and to join him in struggling for it (1:27b). Paul notes the privileges of heavenly “citizenship” in 3:20; here in 1:27b-28a he outlines its duties.”¹⁷ Further, Holloway footnote (16) on page 179: “There are a number of linguistic parallels between Phil. 3:20-21 and 2:6-11. It seems more likely that 3:20-21 purposefully reproduces terminology from 2:6-11 in order to link the two passages, the exaltation of Christ anticipating the exaltation of the Christ-believer (However, Holloway admits in the footnote (16) that the passage could be considered a “hymnic fragment”).¹⁸ The passage that Holloway is referring to (Phil. 2:6-11) is often referred to in Bible commentaries and by

¹⁵ James Fowler provides context for the term “paradigm shift” in his book where he discusses how changes in belief systems and understandings of faith can represent paradigm shifts. James W. Fowler, *Stages of Faith: The Psychology of Human Development and the Quest for Meaning* (San Francisco: Harper & Row, 1981), 8.

¹⁶ Paul Holloway writes in his footnote at (17) on (pg) 179: “The contrast is both spatial and temporal. This is characteristic of Jewish and early Christian apocalypticism, of which Paul offers no clearer expression.” Paul A. Holloway, *Philippians: A Commentary*, ed. Adela Yarbro Collins (Minneapolis: Fortress Press, 2017), Hermeneia series, 179.

¹⁷ Paul Holloway has additional insights at footnote (6): “Along with “joy” (Greek: “χαρά” Strong’s #5479 *Mounce’s Expository Dictionary* (pg) 1309), “gospel” (Greek: “εὐαγγέλιον” Strong’s #2098 *Mounce’s Expository Dictionary* (pg) 1159) is a leitmotif in Philippians, occurring nine times. The Philippians are Paul’s partners in the gospel (Phil. 1:5) and by their gift are sharing in his defense of it (Phil. 1:7; 2:16) in a Roman court. Paul takes comfort in the progress of the gospel (Phil. 1:12), which is what really matters, and he speaks approvingly of those who struggle in the gospel alongside him (Phil. 2:22; 4:3). In Phil. 4:15 he speaks of the “beginning of the gospel,” by which it is clear that what he means by “gospel” is the gentile mission.” At footnote (7) is where Holloway annotates: “Paul notes the privileges of heavenly “citizenship” in 3:20.” Paul A. Holloway, *Philippians: A Commentary*, ed. Adela Yarbro Collins (Minneapolis: Fortress Press, 2017), Hermeneia series, 105; William D. Mounce, *Mounce’s Complete Expository Dictionary of Old and New Testament Words* (Grand Rapids, MI: Zondervan, 2006), 1159 & 1309.

¹⁸ Paul Holloway states in footnotes (16) and (17): Phil. 2:6-11 is a “hymnic fragment” and not a hymn, but upholds that Phil. 3:20-21 has apocalyptic language. Paul A. Holloway, *Philippians: A Commentary*, ed. Adela Yarbro Collins (Minneapolis: Fortress Press, 2017), Hermeneia series, 179.

scholars as the “Christ Hymn,” a powerful passage where Paul presents Jesus’ humility, incarnation, and exaltation.¹⁹

Holloway’s commentary emphasizes the dual nature of “citizenship” in Philippians, where Paul not only highlights its privileges but also stresses its responsibilities. In Philippians 1:27, Paul urges the believers to live in a way that honors the gospel, linking this conduct to the concept of citizenship in heaven, which he elaborates upon in Philippians 3:20.²⁰ Each chapter in Philippians builds upon itself and it is evident in the commentary shared by Holloway.

Holloway further comments on page 180: “Verses 20-21 constitute one of the clearest statements of Paul’s mythology of salvation as metamorphosis: (“who will transform” “μετασχηματίσει” (*metaschēmatisēi*) the body of our humiliation (“to be conformed” “συμμορφίσει” (*symmorphisai*) to his body of glory.”²¹

C. Analysis of the Hermeneia Commentary:

In this commentary, Paul Holloway highlights the detailed theme which is the eschatological focus of “heavenly citizenship” in Philippians, where Paul emphasizes both the

¹⁹ “Christ’s Hymn.” The significance of Phil. 2:6-11 for Paul not only in *Philippians* is such that it deserves to be called his ‘master story,’ his controlling narrative. Gorman footnotes on page (pg.) (491) (4): See chapter (ch.) 4 and especially my *Cruciformity: Paul’s Narrative Spirituality of the Cross* (Grand Rapids: Eerdmans, 2001), (129-169) particularly (ch.) 5. Some scholars have also thought of this text, especially if it is pre-Pauline, as the originating point of *Christology*. Bottom of (pg.) 491: Many scholars have considered it to be an early Christian (pre-Pauline) *hymn* or *hymn fragment*, it is clearly owned and loved by Paul even if he did not compose it. It is also a text that the Philippians may well have heard before. Michael J. Gorman, *Apostle of the Crucified Lord: A Theological Introduction to the Pauline Epistles*, 2nd ed. (Grand Rapids: Eerdmans, 2017), 491.

²⁰ Phil. 1:27 NRSV: “Only, live for your life in a manner worthy of the gospel of Christ, so that, whether I come and see you or am absent and hear about you, I will know that you are *standing firm in one spirit, striving side by side* with one mind for the faith of the gospel.” *The New Oxford Annotated Bible with Apocrypha: New Revised Standard Version* (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2010), 2063, Phil. 1:27

²¹ Greek (Grk) “who will transform” “μετασχηματίσει” (*metaschēmatisēi*) *Mounce’s Expository Dictionary* (pg) 1210 - Strong’s # 3339). (Grk) “to be conformed” “συμμορφίσει” (*symmorphisai*) *Mounce’s Expository Dictionary* (pg) 1285 - Strong’s # 4964). William D. Mounce, *Mounce’s Complete Expository Dictionary of Old and New Testament Words* (Grand Rapids, MI: Zondervan, 2006), 1210 & 1285. Paul A. Holloway, *Philippians: A Commentary*, ed. Adela Yarbro Collins (Minneapolis: Fortress Press, 2017), Hermeneia series, 180.

privileges and responsibilities of being a citizen of heaven. In Philippians 1:27, Paul encourages the Philippians to live in a manner that reflects the gospel, underscoring the duties associated with their heavenly citizenship. Holloway also draws attention to the intentional linguistic connections between Philippians 2:6-11, often called the “Christ Hymn,” and Philippians 3:20-21, suggesting that Paul purposefully echoes themes of Christ’s exaltation to illustrate the anticipated exaltation for believers who share in His humility and mission. Lastly, Holloway highlights in verses 20-21 a significant aspect of Paul’s *soteriology*, where he articulates the transformative process of salvation as a metamorphosis, emphasizing that believers will undergo a profound change from their current “body of humiliation” to a glorified state in alignment with “Christ’s own body of glory”.²²

D. Word Biblical Commentary:

Gerald Hawthorne writes in reference to Phil. 3:20: “But the conjunction that connects this section with the section before it (vv. 18-19) hardly seems capable of doing so. It is the conjunction (“for”) and in Greek (“γὰρ” or “gar”) whose normal function is to introduce the reason or cause for that which has just been mentioned.²³ Paul has just finished saying that the enemies of the cross of Christ are people whose minds are fixed on “earthly things”. Now he continues with “For our citizenship is in heaven....” This presents such a difficulty that the

²² The (Grk) noun “σωτήρ” or “sótér” which translates to “a Savior,” “deliverer,” or “preserver”. The Strong’s # is 4990 and is used 24 times in the Bible. Sótér is the root of the theological term, *soteriology* (“the study of *salvation* through Christ”). The usage of note is Phil. 3:20 where it says in the NET Bible translation: “we also eagerly await a savior”. William D. Mounce, *Mounce’s Complete Expository Dictionary of Old and New Testament Words* (Grand Rapids, MI: Zondervan, 2006), 1287.

²³ The Greek (Grk) conjunction and term “γὰρ” or “gar” Strong’s # 1063 is frequently used with an ellipsis of the clause to which it has reference. William D. Mounce, *Mounce’s Complete Expository Dictionary of Old and New Testament Words* (Grand Rapids, MI: Zondervan, 2006), 1111.

earliest quotations of this passage by Greek authors substitute (“but”) for (“for”) and modern versions translate as (“but”) and in Greek (“ἀλλά” or “alla”).²⁴ Here in Philippians 3:20, “for” connects the verse more closely with the preceding thought in Philippians 3:19 about those who are focused on “earthly things.” Rather than setting up a direct contrast (“but”), (“for”) suggests an explanatory reason, implying that the believers’ heavenly citizenship is a foundational truth explaining why their focus should not be on earthly matters.²⁵

Gerald Hawthorne writes in reference to Philippians 3:20-21 on pages 168-69: “This section seems not to fit easily with the context in which it is placed. Its apocalyptic theme of the church as a colony of heaven, eagerly expecting a savior to come from above to set everything right, to deliver it from its present moral weakness, and to transfigure it from lowliness to glory, is unexpected to say the least. Nothing that has immediately preceded these verses has prepared the reader for this kind of happy outburst.”²⁶

Further, Hawthorne expands his sentiments on page 169: “There has been no recounting of suffering, no tale of woe, no despairing of life as things that would naturally give rise to such an affirmation of hopeful confidence of deliverance in the future.”²⁷

²⁴ The (Grk) conjunction and term “ἀλλά” or “alla” Strong’s # 235 serves to introduce a sentence with keenness and emphasis. William D. Mounce, *Mounce’s Complete Expository Dictionary of Old and New Testament Words* (Grand Rapids, MI: Zondervan, 2006), 1077.

²⁵ Hawthorne is discussing the dilemma and controversy that is caused with by conjunction in the Greek of “For” versus “But”. This is more evidence to support Michael Gorman and his assertion that the NRSV should be used for exegesis unless it is coming from the original Greek or Hebrew. Gerald F. Hawthorne, *Philippians*, Vol. 43 of *Word Biblical Commentary*, ed. David A. Hubbard and Glenn W. Barker (Waco, TX: Word Books Publisher, 1983), 169.

²⁶ On Page 168 Hawthorne footnotes on verse (v) 21 of (a) and (b): (a) Many texts add a Greek phrase before “become” and several texts omit several Greek words from 21. (b) At the word “himself” and Hawthorne notes that read as “to himself” and its variances simply and precisely causes ambiguity contained in the Greek. This is why Michael Gorman reiterates to ministers and students to use the NRSV for exegesis. Gerald F. Hawthorne, *Philippians*, Vol. 43 of *Word Biblical Commentary*, ed. David A. Hubbard and Glenn W. Barker (Waco, TX: Word Books Publisher, 1983), 168-169.

²⁷ Hawthorne is talking about how amidst all calamity and chaos that the Apostle Paul seems to have amnesia and takes in great joy amidst adversity. I contend that Paul is building a crescendo of great magnitude in Paul’s Opus to contrast “earth” versus “heaven.” Gerald F. Hawthorne, *Philippians*, Vol. 43 of *Word Biblical Commentary*, ed. David A. Hubbard and Glenn W. Barker (Waco, TX: Word Books Publisher, 1983), 169.

On page 170 Hawthorne ties his thoughts together with contextualization: “Jews are people whose minds are earth-bound since the earth is the limit of their mental horizon; Christians have their minds fixed on heaven from where they eagerly expect the Savior to come. Jews expect perfection now by keeping the Law; Christians yearn for the future at which time perfection will be achieved. Jews stand as enemies of the crucified Christ; Christians own Christ as Lord and see him as sovereign over the universe. Jews will find their end to be destruction, however ecstatic and glorious their present may be; Christians may be straining now, morally struggling to attain. Their weak mortal bodies will be transformed and made like Christ’s resplendent body.”²⁸

E. Analysis of the Word Biblical Commentary:

Hawthorne’s commentary contrasts between earthly and heavenly perspectives, presenting Jewish focus as limited to the present world, while Christians are depicted as looking toward a future hope rooted in Christ’s return (Greek noun “parousia” “παρουσία” which translates to “presence” or “arrival”).²⁹ This reflection challenges believers to live with a forward-looking faith, enduring present struggles with the assurance of ultimate transformation and union with Christ’s glory. By setting their sights on a future perfected state, Christians are reminded that present hardships are temporary and purposeful. Hawthorne’s perspective encourages a mindset of perseverance, one that values spiritual growth over immediate gratification. In this way,

²⁸ Gerald Hawthorne comments on page 170: “Our citizenship in heaven,” stands first in this new section. It has the emphatic position as in v. 3 in order again to draw sharp contrast between “them” and “us,” between Jews and Christians. Their citizenship is on earth v. 19; ours is in heaven. The word translated “citizenship” is found only here in the NT, is more accurately translated “commonwealth” or “state.” Gerald F. Hawthorne, *Philippians*, Vol. 43 of *Word Biblical Commentary*, ed. David A. Hubbard and Glenn W. Barker (Waco, TX: Word Books Publisher, 1983), 170.

²⁹ The Greek (Grk) noun “παρουσία” or “parousia” meaning “a coming,” “arrival,” “advent”. The Strong’s # is 3952. It is referenced in Phil. 1:26 and Phil. 2:12 and 24 times in the Bible. William D. Mounce, *Mounce’s Complete Expository Dictionary of Old and New Testament Words* (Grand Rapids, MI: Zondervan, 2006), 1237.

believers are called to adopt a faith that is both patient and resilient, trusting in the promise of a future beyond the limitations of earthly existence. Hawthorne’s insight stresses that this forward-looking faith is not passive, but actively shapes how believers respond to their current situation in life. By holding onto the vision that Paul is communicating, Christians can find strength to navigate trials, seeing them as part of a larger narrative of redemption. This future oriented perspective also fosters a sense of communal purpose, as the church collectively anticipates Christ’s return and supports one another in maintaining faith amid the difficulties of earthly life.

V. Conclusion:

This exegetical study of Paul’s letter and the metaphor of “heavenly citizenship” versus “earthly citizenship” challenge the Philippians to prioritize their relationship with Christ above their earthly affiliations, particularly in the face of Roman civic pride (Latin: “superbia civica”)³⁰ The Greek noun (“*politeuma*” or “πολίτευμα”), which appears in Philippians 3:20, translates to “citizenship,” “commonwealth,” “state,” or “form of government.”³¹ This term emphasizes the believers’ identity and allegiance as members of God’s heavenly kingdom. In contrast, the Greek verb (“*politeuomai*” or “πολιτεύομαι”), meaning “to live as a citizen,” appears in Philippians 1:27, urging believers to conduct themselves in a manner worthy of this divine citizenship.³²

Phil. 1:27 is what Holloway and Hawthorne are linking together with Phil. 3:20-21. I agree with

³⁰ Stephen Davis discusses the topic of Roman “civic pride” (Latin: “superbia civica”) at length in his book. Stephen T. Davis, *Civic Pride and Moral Order in the Roman World* (London: Routledge, 2002), 58-60.

³¹ The Greek (Grk) tword “πολίτευμα” or “politeuma” is equivalent to “the administration of a commonwealth” or “a community” or “commonwealth” Strong’s #4175. William D. Mounce, *Mounce’s Complete Expository Dictionary of Old and New Testament Words* (Grand Rapids, MI: Zondervan, 2006), 1249.

³² The (Grk) term or word “πολιτεύομαι” or “politeuomai” is equivalent to “to be a citizen,” “to govern a city or state,” “administer,” the affairs of a state,” “to be governed,” “to order one’s life and conduct,” “converse,” or “live (in a certain manner as to habits and principles)” Strong’s #4176. William D. Mounce, *Mounce’s Complete Expository Dictionary of Old and New Testament Words* (Grand Rapids, MI: Zondervan, 2006), 1249-1250.

them both and believe that this is the most common linkage amongst theologians and scholars.

However, my assertion or addition to this exegetical study is that we should look back at Philippians 3:19. Near the end of verse 19 it ends with the Greek adjective (“*epigeios*” or “ἐπίγειος”), meaning “of [on] the earth.”³³ This term would have resonated with the Philippians, who, as residents of a Roman colony, understood the privileges and prestige associated with Roman citizenship. In contrasting *politeuma* “citizenship” in Phil 3:20-21 with *epigeios* or “of [on] the earth” in Philippians 3:19, Paul provides a powerful parallel for understanding the believers’ ultimate allegiance and identity as belonging to God’s kingdom instead “of [on] the earth.” Hawthorne also echoes this in his commentary on *Philippians*. Essentially, Paul is alluding and pointing believers to focus their attention to “heaven” and for believers to take their attention completely off of “earthly things” as Hawthorne notes.

Although my word study differs slightly from the two commentaries I agree wholeheartedly with both Holloway and Hawthorne and their analyses. The interpretation of “glorious body” found in verse 21 with “transformation” provided by the commentaries, highlights the eschatological promise that believers’ bodies will be transformed to “Christ’s glorified body.” Paul’s promise of transformation serves as both encouragement and motivation for the Philippians and believers to live with hope and an eternal mindset. Paul’s message to the Philippians, therefore, is not simply a theological concept but a practical directive, persuading them to embody their “heavenly citizenship” in their daily lives. By anchoring their identity in Christ, they are encouraged to resist the pressures of conforming to the prevailing Roman cultural expectations, instead of embodying values that honor their divine allegiance to Christ. This perspective also serves to unify the Philippian community, fostering a collective conscience

³³ The Greek (Grk) adjective “ἐπίγειος” or “*epigeios*” is equivalent to “on the earth,” “earthly,” “terrestrial,” “earthly, low, groveling” Strong’s #1919. It is mentioned 7 times in the Bible. Of note vv Phil. 2:10 and Phil. 3:19. William D. Mounce, *Mounce’s Complete Expository Dictionary of Old and New Testament Words* (Grand Rapids, MI: Zondervan, 2006), 1151.

rooted in shared hope and purpose as they anticipate God's promise.

To close this exegetical study, I will quote the scholar Stanley Porter who states in his book *The Apostle Paul* where he touchingly writes: “*Philippians* is a well-loved Pauline letter, because of its ‘Christ hymn’ (Phil. 2:6-11). However, a number of critical issues regarding *Philippians* sometimes *preoccupy* scholars, rather than appreciating its positive and encouraging message from Paul to a beloved church. I first discuss the city of Philippi, and then treat authorship, literary integrity, the opponents, occasion, and purpose, and date and place of writing, before concluding with an outline and its content.”³⁴ I encourage students, expositors, interpreters, ministers, and professors who are studying the Apostle Paul to read the book by Stanley Porter. Porter's structured and methodical approach to understanding and interpreting Paul's letter to the *Philippians* is foundational because Porter first sets up the historical and cultural context of *Philippi*. Lastly, his analysis methodically addresses key scholarly debates where he ensures maximum coverage, and he examines factors such as authorship and the letter's intended audience. By exploring these critical aspects, Porter provides readers with a foundation that cultivates their understanding of Paul's underlying message (his theology) and emphasizes the letter's pastoral and theological significance.

³⁴ Stanley E. Porter, *The Apostle Paul: His Life, Thought, and Letters* (Grand Rapids, MI: William B. Eerdmans Publishing Company, 2016), 382.

A Touching Note:

Finally, one of the verses in *Philippians* that brought great encouragement to my wife and I during her recent hospitalization (October 18 – 22, 2024, health scare and complications from surgery), specifically while we were in room 419 is Philippians 4:19. The Apostle Paul proclaims in verse 19: “And my God will fully satisfy every need of yours according to his riches in glory in Christ Jesus.”³⁵ This promise reassured us of God’s provision and care during a challenging time, reminding us that your needs would be met through the abundance of His grace in Christ Jesus. This verse serves as a powerful reminder of God’s faithfulness, especially in moments of uncertainty, despair, and need.

³⁵ Verses (vv) 15,17,18: Giving and receiving, profit...account, paid in full, a series of business terms used metaphorically here and in other contexts of friendship. Verse (v) 18 just before v 19 notes the *Fragrant offering* (Mentioned in Gen 8:21. Ex. 29:18, Ezek. 20:41). Verse 18: “I have been paid in full and have more than enough; I am fully satisfied, now that I have received from Epaphroditus the gifts you sent, a fragrant offering, a sacrifice acceptable and pleasing to God.” *The New Oxford Annotated Bible with Apocrypha: New Revised Standard Version* (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2010), 2065, Phil. 4:18-19.

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